

Asymmetric hydrogenation of *N*-heterocycles with sodium cyanoborohydride and *S*-(-)-binol

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Abstract : Asymmetric hydrogenation of indole-3-aldehydes, indazole-3-aldehyde and aza indole-3-aldehydes with sodium cyanoborohydride and *S*-binol under glac. acetic acid over a period of 1–2 h gave enantiomeric excess of 3-substituted 2,3-dihydro alcohols in good yields. This is the first report for the hydrogenation of aromatic compounds like indoles, indazoles and aza indoles with mild reducing catalyst sodium cyanoborohydride.

Keywords : Asymmetric hydrogenation, NaCNBH₃, dihydro compounds, enantiomeric excess.

Introduction

Hydrogenation is the simplest but most powerful way to produce a wide array of important compounds in large quantities using inexpensive, clean hydrogen gas without forming any waste. Asymmetric hydrogenation was very important method to synthesize the optically active enantiomerically enriched compounds in industry^{1,2}. For many applications, no enantioselective catalytic method exists and the chiral auxiliary based protocols are the only available stereoselective method. Chiral auxiliaries are enantiomerically pure compounds that are linked to a substrate and influence the stereo chemical course of a reaction³.

The asymmetric hydrogenation of aromatic and heteroaromatic compounds would appear to be the most attractive and challenge method for the enantioselective synthesis of carbocyclic and heterocyclic compounds^{4–7}. However some of the compounds exhibit with moderate enantio selectivity depends on unique catalyst systems, but strain from lack of suitable substrates, have been described so far^{8,9}. Thus it would appear worthwhile to explore novel protocols for asymmetric hydrogenation of heteroaromatic compounds because of the usefulness and advantages of such methods would accrue in the preparation of optically active heterocyclic compounds.

Sodium cyano borohydride reduces aldehydes and ketones to the corresponding alcohols under acidic conditions (at pH 3–4)^{10,11}. The reduction of a series of conjugated ketones of the cholestenone type with sodium cyanoborohydride in tetrahydro furan solvent results the corresponding allylic alcohol¹². Under acid conditions, the reduction of ketoximes with sodium cyano borohydride in methanol and HCl proceeds smoothly to the corresponding *N*-alkyl hydroxyl amine (at pH 3) and *N,N*-dialkyl hydroxyl amine (at pH 4)¹⁰. Simple enamines are rapidly reduced by sodium cyanoborohydride in 15 : 1 tetrahydrofuran and methanol solvent mixture at pH 5¹⁰. The reaction of a ketone with amines or hydroxyl amine undergo reduction with sodium cyano borohydride in methanol solvent at pH yielded corresponding *N*-alkyl amines and *N*-alkyl hydroxyl amines¹⁰. The reaction of a dicarbonyl compound with primary amine in the presence of sodium cyano borohydride provides the new synthesis of nitrogen heterocycles without effecting the pyridine and indole moieties^{10,13}. The reductive amination with sodium cyano borohydride under mild conditions gave amino ester, amino epoxide, amino nitroxide free radical, amino ketone and amino lactone^{10,14–17}. Sodium cyano borohydride performed a new methodology for the

protecting group free synthesis of primary amines by the ammonia mediated reductive amination of aldehydes and hemiacetals¹⁸. Giese reaction, tin-free Giese reaction and the related radical carbonylation processes are proceeded chemoselectively at the carbon-iodine bond side with sodium cyano borohydride^{19,20}.

Importantly, a survey of the literature revealed that the catalytic hydrogenation of heteroaromatic compounds with sodium cyano borohydride has not been reported. Now, I plan asymmetric hydrogenation of *N*-heterocyclic compounds with sodium cyano borohydride and using catalytic amount of chiral auxiliaries. Here I propose the use of catalytic amount of bidentate chiral auxiliaries for the asymmetric hydrogenation of *N*-heteroaromatic compounds. The asymmetric hydrogenation of indoles, aza indoles and indazole with sodium cyano borohydride and binol was shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Asymmetric hydrogenation of indoles, indazoles and aza indoles by NaCNBH₃.

Results and discussion

To optimize the reaction conditions, we had investigated the hydrogenation of indole-3-aldehydes, aza indole-3-aldehydes and indazole-3-aldehydes with sodium cyano borohydrides in different solvent systems. The hydrogenation of the above compounds in methanol solvent can't proceed successfully. A small amount of HCl was added to the methanol solvent (up to pH 3–4) and the hydrogenation reaction was performed. At this time, we observed only indole-3-carbinols, aza indole-3-carbinols

and indazole-3-carbinol in good yield. Now we replace the methanol with glacial acetic acid and pH reaches less than 1 value. The hydrogenation of the starting molecules were performed with sodium cyano borohydride and *S*-(-)-binol as a chiral auxiliary in glacial acetic acid then enantiomeric excess of dihydro indole carbinols, dihydro aza indole carbinols and dihydro indazole carbinol were obtained. All the reactions occurred in 1–2 h only. The reaction conditions and enantiomeric excess data are shown in Table 1.

Conclusion

Asymmetric hydrogenation of indole-3-aldehydes, indazole-3-aldehyde and aza indole-3-aldehydes with sodium cyanoborohydride and *S*-binol under glac. acetic acid over a period of 1–2 h gave enantiomeric excess of 3-substituted 2,3-dihydro alcohols in good yields. This is the first report for the hydrogenation of aromatic compounds like indoles, indazoles and aza indoles with mild reducing catalyst sodium cyanoborohydride.

Experimental

General :

All chemicals and reagents were obtained from Aldrich (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA), Lancaster (Alfa Aesar, Johnson Matthey Company, Ward Hill, MA, USA) and were used without further purification. Reactions were monitored by TLC, performed on silica gel glass plates containing 60 F-254, and visualization on TLC was achieved by UV light or iodine indicator. Proton spectra was recorded on a Gemini Varian-VXR-unity (300 MHz) instrument. Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in ppm downfield from internal TMS standard. Mass ESI spectra were recorded on Micro mass, Quattro LC using ESI+ software with capillary voltage 3.98 kV and ESI mode positive ion trap detector. The enantiomeric excess (ee) was determined using HPLC (Shimadzu prominence) con-

Table 1. The reaction conditions and enantiomeric excess data

Entry	P	Q	R	R ¹	X	Time	Yield (%)	ee (%)
2a	CH	CH	H	H	CH	1 h 15 min	78	45
2b	CH	CH	H	CH ₃	CH	1 h 5 min	71	10
2c	CH	N	H	H	CH	1 h 30 min	82	87
2d	N	CH	H	H	CH	2 h	74	34
2e	CH	CH	Br	H	NH	1 h 10 min	85	7

nected to chiral column AD-H. The solvent system used is isopropanol : hexane (1 : 9) with the flow rate of 1.0 mL/min.

General procedure :

Compound (1) (1 g, 1 eq.) was dissolved in acetic acid (5 mL) and cooled to 15 °C by using aq. NaCl and ice. Sodium cyanoborohydride (1 g, 3.15 eq.) was added in portions to this cooled solution. To the above mixture 5 mol% *S*-(-)-binol was added. After the addition was complete, stirring was continued for 1 h at room temperature. Subsequently, water (15 mL) was added and after 15 min at room temperature, the mixture was evaporated under reduced pressure at 60 °C. To the residue was added 30 mL of aq. NaHCO₃, ethylacetate and the organic layer was washed with brine (25 mL). After drying over Na₂SO₄, the solvent was removed by evaporation under reduced pressure to afford pure compounds. All the synthesized compounds are colorless liquids.

Spectral data of synthesized compounds :

[2,3-Dihydro-1*H*-indol-3-yl]methanol : Yield : 78%; [α]_D²⁵ = +46.7 (*c* 0.7, CHCl₃); IR (neat) : 3455, 3272, 3052, 1520, 1298, 752 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.19–7.08 (2H, m), 6.76 (1H, t, *J* 7.1 Hz), 6.49 (1H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz), 3.97 (1H, br s, -NH), 3.88–3.79 (2H, m), 3.56–3.48 (1H, br s), 3.38 (2H, m), 3.11 (1H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 40.3, 50.6, 66.9, 111.7, 114.1, 123.9, 127.3, 129.6, 144.7; MS (ESI) : *m/z* = 150 (M+H)⁺.

[1-Methyl-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-indol-3-yl]methanol : Yield : 71%; [α]_D²⁵ = +192.3 (*c* 1.1, CHCl₃); IR (neat) : 3435, 3058, 1598, 1370, 760 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.16–7.05 (2H, m), 6.72 (1H, t, *J* 6.7 Hz), 6.52 (1H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz), 3.83–3.70 (2H, m), 3.44 (1H, br s), 3.34 (2H, m), 3.28 (1H, m), 2.78 (3H, s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 33.4, 41.2, 61.3, 64.9, 109.9, 121.2, 124.6, 125.0, 128.9, 145.1; MS (ESI) : *m/z* = 164 (M+H)⁺.

[2,3-Dihydro-1*H*-pyrrolo[2,3-*b*]pyridin-3-yl]methanol : Yield : 82%; [α]_D²⁵ = -6.3 (*c* 0.9, CHCl₃); IR (neat) : 3436, 3260, 2955, 1560, 1222, 756 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.06 (1H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz), 7.29 (1H, d, *J* 6.9 Hz), 6.51 (1H, t, *J* 7.5, 6.8 Hz), 4.12 (1H, br s), 3.94–3.85 (2H, m), 3.49 (2H, m), 3.21 (1H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 43.4, 48.6, 66.7, 124.0,

133.1, 142.5, 147.6; MS (ESI) : *m/z* = 151 (M+H)⁺.

[2,3-Dihydro-1*H*-pyrrolo[3,2-*b*]pyridin-3-yl]methanol : Yield : 74%; [α]_D²⁵ = -54.8 (*c* 0.4, CHCl₃); IR (neat) : 3459, 3250, 2977, 1557, 1224, 761 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 8.33 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz), 7.23–7.14 (2H, m), 4.06 (1H, br s), 3.88–3.76 (2H, m), 3.58 (1H, br s), 3.39 (2H, m), 3.27 (1H, m); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 40.2, 44.6, 62.1, 117.7, 126.2, 137.8, 140.4, 143.6; MS (ESI) : *m/z* = 151 (M+H)⁺.

[5-Bromo-2,3-dihydro-1*H*-indazol-3-yl]methanol : Yield : 85%; [α]_D²⁵ = +114.3 (*c* 0.9, CHCl₃); IR (neat) : 3459, 3256, 2967, 1557, 757, 670 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.51 (1H, s), 7.32 (1H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 6.88 (1H, d, *J* 8.3 Hz), 4.11 (1H, br s), 4.02–3.91 (2H, m), 3.88 (1H, m), 3.59 (2H, br s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 62.4, 63.6, 103.4, 114.7, 123.6, 127.2, 130.1, 146.7; MS (ESI) : *m/z* = 230 (M+H)⁺.

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